

INTRODUCTION OF INNOVATIVE BANKING SERVICES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF COMMERCIAL BANKS

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Abstract. This article talks about the development of commercial banks, the wider application of scientific and technological innovations in banking practice. Opinions and conclusions are given at the end of the article.

Keywords: banking activity, technology, modernization, innovative banking services.

Significant positive changes were observed in the banking system in our Republic during the years of independence. In particular, a number of important laws defining the legal basis of the activity of commercial banks have been adopted, and great conditions are being created for the development of this sector as a producer of the national economy. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On additional measures to increase the popularity of banking services" dated 03/23/2018. It should be noted that the necessary legal framework for the implementation of PQ-3620 has been formed, practical economic incentives and innovations and preferences have been created for its active development, the licensing system has been significantly simplified and liberalized. It is very important to develop banking activities, to use scientific and technological innovations more widely in the practice of banking activities. In the conditions of economic liberalization and modernization, one of the main tasks in serving production and service enterprises is to offer high-quality, cheap and convenient services. This, in turn, means that commercial banks should improve innovative banking services and increase the quality of their control, develop practical recommendations aimed at improving the quality of work of commercial banks in our Republic based on the experience and practice of international commercial banks.

Innovative banking services play an extremely important role in the modern economy and financial services market. Because customers are served remotely. Remote bank account servicing systems are technologies for providing banking services based on the customer's orders from a distance (without coming to the bank). It is mainly carried out through computer and telephone networks.

Types of remote bank account servicing systems: Bank-Client is a computer-based system in which a special program is installed on the client's computer. This

program stores all customer information (mainly payment documents and account statements) on the computer. Bank and a direct connection is made between the client's computer through a modem. Internet banking is a system that allows customers to manage deposit accounts, including accounts opened for plastic cards, via the Internet. This type of service is a system designed for making payments in real time while the client is connected to the bank remotely. The user accesses the system through a web browser. The Internet banking system is hosted on the bank's web server. The user has the opportunity to view all his information (payment documents and account statements) on the bank's website. Through the Internet banking service, the client can:

- make payments at his workplace or in other convenient conditions;
- monitoring the stages of payment;
- provides access to all operations at any time, such as receiving all reports.

Through Internet banking, the client can connect to the bank's website from his workplace and see the money coming into his account, prepare money transfers and send them to the bank. The mobile banking system is based on internet banking technology. It is also used by applications such as MBANK. Each financial credit organization, that is, banks, develops applications under their logos and provides services to their clients. This program (application) is a mobile application for mobile phones running on Android and iOS platforms. They include:

- Formation of messages and notifications;
- Preparation of electronic settlement documents;
- Send payment orders;
- Enables services such as account management.

This type of service is available for mobile phone users using iOS or Android operating systems, and these applications are constantly being updated. DISCUSSION SMS-banking is a system of receiving information in the form of SMS to bank customers about transactions in their deposit accounts and accounts opened for plastic cards. Previously, in order to get information from the account, the client had to send an SMS request to a special phone number of the bank. Currently, information about transactions in the account is sent automatically to the subscriber's number with SMS notification. The SMS-banking service allows the client to perform the following actions:

- funds received in the account;
- expenses made from the account;
- account balance;
- provides an opportunity to obtain operational information about bank operations conducted during the day.

"Internet banking" service is a bank for customers in the form of online payment

It is being used by bank clients because it enables remote payments for services, taxes, state duties, and other payments without coming to the bank building. Year after year, as a result of the introduction of discounts and the creation of convenience, banks offer customers to familiarize themselves with and use the electronic payment system "Internetbanking", which is considered one of the types of modern banking services. For this purpose, on the website of the banks and in the customer service department of the bank branches, the work of explaining to the customers is carried out by connecting to the "Internet-banking" system. This system is a computer software system that allows the client to manage and control his bank account without leaving the office (home), as a result of using communication channels (the Internet)

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